

Business in Social Media: From Idea to Tax Awareness

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◆ Abstract

The project “Business in Social Media: From Idea to Tax Awareness” was developed and submitted within the framework of the international grant program **Skill.ED – 2025 of the Kronospan Foundation** (more information: <https://kronospanfoundation.org/skilled-2025/>).

The Skill.ED program aims to support general, vocational, and technical education by funding innovative educational initiatives and strengthening the practical component of learning .

The project is implemented by the Department of Accounting and Taxation of Uman National University and focuses on supporting veterans, their family members, and internally displaced persons. It is based on the course “Business in Social Media: Accounting and Taxation” and aims to expand its practical component through the integration of digital tools and blended learning approaches.

The training program includes **7 lecture modules and 5 practical workshops**, with a total workload of approximately **35–40 academic hours**. The educational process is supported through Moodle and a dedicated Telegram platform, microlearning video lessons, and consultations. Participants gain competencies in social media marketing, content creation, online sales, financial planning, bookkeeping, tax calculation, and compliance with Ukrainian taxation requirements for individual entrepreneurs (FOP).

A key component of the project is the establishment of a **Digital Business Hub**, a modern educational laboratory equipped for training and content creation. The total project budget amounts to approximately **€9,975**, which corresponds to the funding limits of the Skill.ED program (up to €10,000 per project).

The project is expected to engage **60–80 participants**, with the possibility of scaling up to 100 in an online format. Expected outcomes include the launch of new small businesses, increased self-employment, and employment in SMM and financial consulting.

The project contributes to strengthening financial literacy, entrepreneurial thinking, and social integration, particularly for vulnerable groups. It represents a replicable

model of combining higher education, digital tools, and practical business training to support sustainable economic development in Ukraine.

◆ **Keywords**

entrepreneurship, financial literacy, social media business, taxation, digital education, Ukraine